

Complex Compounds of N-Amidino-S-ethylthiourea with Co (II), Ni (II) and Cu (II)

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N-amidino-S-ethylthiourea (HASETU) reacts with Co (II), Ni (II) and Cu (II) in ammoniacal solution to form complexes of the type $M(\text{ASETU})_2$, where $M = \text{Co}$, Ni or Cu. The magnetic susceptibility of the complexes has been studied in the range 85°-300°K and their structures are discussed.

The metal complexes of substituted amidinothiourea have not been investigated though complex compounds of amidinothiourea ($\text{H}_2\text{N}-\text{C}-\text{NH}-\text{C}-\text{NH}_2$) with transition

metal ions are known. On the basis of colour of cobalt, nickel and copper complexes and their decomposition reactions with alkali, Ray and co-workers¹⁻³ have suggested that this ligand reacts in the thiol-form ($\text{HN}=\text{C}-\text{NH}-\text{C}-\text{NH}_2$) with cobalt and copper to

form compounds which may be formulated as follows:

A study of the reactions of substituted amidinothiourea with metal ions is expected to throw light on the structures of amidinothiourea complexes. In the present communication the preparation and properties of the compounds of N-amidino-S-ethylthiourea ($\text{HN}=\text{C}-\text{NH}-\text{C}-\text{NH}_2$) with cobalt (II), nickel (II) and copper (II) are described and

$\text{H}_2\text{C}_2-\text{S} \quad \text{NH}$
 their structures are discussed.

1. Chaudhury and Ray, *this Journal*, 1950, 27, 673.
2. Poddar and Ray, *Ibid*, 1952, 29, 279.
3. Ray, *Chem. Rev.*, 1961, 61, 513.

EXPERIMENTAL

Hydrobromide of *N*-amidino-*S*-ethylthiourea was prepared by the method of Kurzer⁴. The compound was recrystallised from ether-ethanol mixture and dried over anhydrous CaCl_2 under vacuum (m.p. 180°C).

	C	H	N	S	Br
	%	%	%	%	%
Found:	22.7	4.9	23.9	13.99	34.7
Required for $\text{C}_4\text{H}_{11}\text{N}_4\text{SBr}$:	21.14	4.88	24.6	14.11	35.2

Preparation of cobalt (II), nickel (II) and copper (II) complexes of N-amidino-S-ethylthiourea: (HASETU).

100 ml. of 0.2M solution of *N*-amidino-*S*-ethylthiourea hydrobromide in water were added to a mixture of 100 ml. of 0.1M metal chloride solution + 10 ml. of 10% NH_4Cl solution. It was then followed by addition of 30 ml. of 1:1 NH_4OH till the precipitation was complete (pH=9.5). The coloured precipitate was allowed to settle and then filtered. It was washed with water, alcohol and ether and dried over anhydrous CaCl_2 under vacuum. The precipitate of cobalt (II) complex was washed only with water since it turned black when washed with alcohol and ether. The metal complexes were analysed for metal ion, sulphur, nitrogen carbon and hydrogen.

Magnetic Susceptibility measurements: Low temperature magnetic susceptibility measurements were taken on Gouy balance as described by Figgis and Nyholm⁵. The accuracy of the measurements was within 1%.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of chemical analysis (table 1) indicate that the complexes of *N*-amidino-*S*-ethylthiourea with Co (II), Ni (II) and Cu (II) may be represented as $\text{M}(\text{ASETU})_2$ where M is Co (II), Ni (II) or Cu (II). Cobalt and nickel complexes do not undergo decomposition on heating up to 120°C . The copper complex starts losing its pink colour at around 60°C and at 100°C its colour changes into olive green (table 2). These compounds can be preserved at room temperature in a desiccator. The molecular weights of these compounds could not be determined because of their insolubility in water and organic solvents. The complexes of nickel and copper are, however, slightly soluble in alcohol and acetone respectively.

Over a temperature range of 85°K to 300°K , $\text{Co}(\text{ASETU})_2$ follows a Curie-Weiss law with $\Theta = 17^\circ\text{K}$. It shows a magnetic moment of 2.26 B. M. at 297°K , which is very close to the values reported for low spin 4 covalent complexes of bivalent cobalt with square-planar stereochemistry.

4. Kurzer, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 1.

5. Figgis and Nyholm, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 331.

TABLE I

Analyses of cobalt (II), nickel (II) and copper (II) complexes of N-amidino-S-ethylthiourea.

	% M	% N	% S	% C	% H
Co (ASETU) ₂ : Found	16.75	32.03	18.25	27.56	5.2
Required for Co (C ₄ H ₉ N ₄ S) ₂ :	16.87	32.05	18.35	27.50	5.19
Ni (ASETU) ₂ : Found:	16.78	32.00	18.2	27.6	5.2
Required for Ni (C ₄ H ₉ N ₄ S) ₂ :	16.82	32.11	18.36	27.53	5.19
Cu (ASETU) ₂ : Found:	18.26	31.52	18.02	27.3	5.0
Required for Cu (C ₄ H ₉ N ₄ S) ₂ :	17.95	31.66	18.11	27.14	5.12

TABLE II

Loss in weight on heating Copper Complex of N-amidino-S-ethylthiourea at different temperatures.

Temp. in C.	50°	60°	70°	80°	85°	90°	100°	110°	120°
% loss in weight	0.10	0.49	4.23	26.05	26.81	27.35	27.5	27.5	27.5

On treatment with dilute alkali Co (ASETU)₂ changes into CoS, a behaviour very similar to that of cobalt (II) complex of amidinothiourea. Considering this reaction as an evidence in favour of Co ← S linkage, it may be represented with a planar six membered ring structure in which the ligand is attached to cobalt through nitrogen and sulphur atoms.

Ni (ASETU)₂ is diamagnetic suggesting a square planar structure involving dsp² hybrid bonds. Since all planar nickel complexes in which the nickel atom is attached to 4 nitrogen atoms are reported to be yellow, orange or red, it is reasonable to assume that the ligand in the orange coloured nickel complex of N-amidino-S-ethylthiourea is attached to nickel atom through nitrogen atoms. Nickel complex of N-amidino-S-ethylthiourea and of amidinothiourea are very similar except that Ni (ASETU)₂ is anhydrous whereas nickel complex of amidinothiourea is hydrated. In view of the close resemblance in properties of nickel complexes of N-amidino-S-ethylthiourea and amidinothiourea a similar structure may be assigned to both.

The magnetic susceptibility of Cu (ASETU)₂ has been studied from 85°K–300°K. It obeys a Curie-Weiss law with a small value of $\Theta = 4^\circ\text{K}$ and μ_{eff} is 1.82 B. M. at 292°K. The magnetic moment so close to spin only value signifies that the orbital contribution is almost completely quenched by the ligand field in the complex.

Cu (ASETU)₂ does not form CuS or copper mercaptan on warming with dil. alkali. On heating it at 120°C. the weight (Table II) change per copper atom corresponds to the loss in weight expected for substitution of -S-C₂H₅ group by -OH group. The olive green product does not give test for sulphur and contains copper and nitrogen in the ratio of 1:8. It is, however, not a copper complex of amidino-urea, which is known to be rose-red, but consists of a mixture of water soluble organic compound and an insoluble green substance containing 44.2% Cu and 19.69%N. Copper complex of N-amidino-S-ethyl-

thiourea differs from that of amidinothiourea in colour and other properties. It may, therefore, be inferred that Cu-S bond is not present in $\text{Cu}(\text{ASETU})_2$ and a six membered ring structure of the complex is formed through nitrogen atoms of the ligand. Apparently, the replacement of H of the thiol group in amidinothiourea by $-\text{C}_6\text{H}_5$ group prevents the formation of $\text{Cu} \leftarrow \text{S}$ bond in $\text{Cu}(\text{ASETU})_2$.

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